

THE ADVANTAGES OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6360185>

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Annotation. This article is devoted to innovative methods of teaching English, the availability of its study by students. The article also discusses the role of lingo-sociocultural understanding in the study of foreign languages.

Key words: Communicative approach, privileges, latest teaching methods, critical thinking, creativity

In our globalized society, the ability to communicate successfully is considered a pivotal skills. The importance of teaching and learning foreign languages is growing with every passing day and a foreign language is not just a subject but a tool for productive cross-cultural communication. The key to communication lies in successful expression of one's intended meaning, which is not as easy as one may hope. Despite a perfect grammar knowledge and the years of study, our students may face difficulty expressing their meaning to native speakers. The problem that comes to light through is that grammar and lexical meaning of words alone cannot guarantee a person the ability to express themselves in a foreign language efficiently. By increasing our students' communicative competence, we will enable them to interact successfully in a foreign language environment. Thus, teaching Communicative competence is the requirement of our modern life.

One of the elements of communicative competence is Sociolinguistic competence that refers to the ability to use language that is appropriate to social contexts. Alptekin explains that social context refers to culture-specific context that include the norms, values, beliefs, and behavioral patterns of a culture [1]. For example, thanking a friend in a formal speech is different from how it is done over a meal.

Communication is an indispensable part of any community life which people feel the need to interact with each other for certain reasons. It is through the concept of language that people can communicate with a number of interlocutors in a variety of settings. However, while interacting, people need to follow need to follow things beyond words. They need to know how to say something as well as when, where and to whom to say it.

Communicative language teaching makes use of real-life situation that necessitate communication. The teacher sets up a situation that students are likely to encounter in real life.

The sociocultural approach which now dominates the educational environment has among its strategic values the formation of cultural awareness, the idea worldview specific to the speaker of the foreign language. The essence of sociocultural approach is in teaching

foreign languages as means of cross-cultural communication and a way to understand foreign cultures and subcultures [8].

Lingo-sociocultural way is originated from language and culture comprehension. Lingo-sociocultural way involves language and cross-cultural aspects of communication. Language is not only vocabulary but it is the way you show and express you. On the west language is “the system of communication”, which consists of particular elements and rules for communication.

Lingo-sociocultural way combines language structures like grammar, vocabulary, etc. with extra linguistic factor. Basically the language structures are sociocultural structures. Therefore, we get to know this world through thinking in certain culture field and use the language for expressing our impressions, ideas, and emotions [2]. The famous specialist in linguistic C.G. Ter -Minasym mentioned in his works that learning English recently became more functional: today request claimed new propositions. [3].

Over the past time new routes have been developed in the search for innovative approaches to the ever urgent problem of foreign language teaching. Whereas several years ago grammar and vocabulary skills, also reading and literature translation were more advantageous, nowadays things are different. Therefore, it is not surprising only people who were really ambitious and hardworking could be fluent in English.

Learning English is as important today as it was not several years ago. Specialist in different fields like cultural, business, science, technics and other spheres of society like communicating with foreign people.

Communicative approach is an innovative way of teaching English and it is on the top of popularity rating among innovative approaches. It is aimed to practice communication. The communicative approach is based on the idea that learning language successfully comes through having to communicate real meaning. When learners are involved in real communication, their natural strategies for language acquisition will be used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language.

Communication is first of all exchanging opinions, information, notions of social, cultural, political and other aspects of everyday life. The world around us is the world of communication in various spheres. The modern communicative method represents a harmonious combination of many ways of teaching foreign languages, being probably, at the top of the evolutionary pyramid of various educational methods. The communicative method develops all language skills- from oral and written speech to reading and listening. The goal is to teach a student to speak a foreign language not only freely, but also correctly. The communicative method sets “open-ended” exercises: everything will depend on the reactions and response. The lesson does not consist of any complicated structure of sentences or vocabulary. As it is known spoken language is quite different than writing [3]. Learners who would like to be professional in particular sphere read publications in appropriate topics in foreign press. Learners can manage to overcome difficulties in reading with their professional vocabulary if they possess plenty of vocabulary skills. It demands a lot of effort to maintain the communication with foreign speaker. Communicative approach helps to overcome the barrier of conversation. A person who has got some skills of grammar structure and vocabulary skills of 600 to 1000 words can easily

manage to have a conversation with foreigners. The last thing that is not less important is learning English expressions like collocations, phrasal verbs, not only separate words. This is way we try to encourage our learners to think in English not to translate from their native language. Oxford and Cambridge approaches are incorporate because many of their courses basically use communicative approach integrated with some traditional elements. If the goal of language teaching is communicative ability on the part of the student, the language teacher must first and foremost take into account four the summarize domains of skills presented here from the student's perspective are as follows:

- The students must develop the skill in manipulating the linguistic system to be able to use it spontaneously and flexibly where the intended message can be expressed.

- The student must develop skills and strategies of using language to communicate meaning as effectively as possible in concrete situations and he must learn to use feedback to judge his success and if necessary, remedy failure by using different language. [4]

To develop autonomous control of the target language of communication, language teachers must at all times allow students autonomy, and conversely discourage them from maintaining dependence. This can be done through provision of international activities with other students, either in person, through pair of group work to achieve the goal of effective communication in the target language. Furthermore, small group work, goal or task-oriented group projects, and formation gathering have been strongly advocated to increase meaningful interactional activities without teacher intervention, and spontaneous language use in authentic communication results in the unconscious development of the target language system [4].

One major disadvantage might be that it is difficult for the teacher alone check the language use of every student, especially in a big class. The students are allowed to make mistakes but they need to be corrected preferably not whilst in the middle of a conversation- by the teacher in order to improve and so as not to make the same mistake again and again. Therefore, it is not helpful if there is only one teacher for one class.

Another point concerning the teacher might be that it depends on the teacher how motivating or boring the lesson will be. The teacher needs to prepare the material at home and needs to make it as motivating and eager to communicate with each other.

Apart from developing language skills Oxford and Cambridge courses trend to creativity and general outlook of students. Whereas language and culture aspects of country are entwined these courses involve cross-cultural aspects [5].

To summarize above, British methods have a range of distinctive. Most of them are basically worked out integrated innovative with traditional ways of teaching. Unchallengeable advantage of British methodologists is making courses with authentic materials, teaching tendency of live and situational English through real life example.

The aim of learning English with the help of this approach is to make it easy to comprehend the companion, to make impressions on the intuitive level. Therefore, it is very important while learning English study history of the national, art, cross-cultural and customs, and the real life situation.

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